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FuturEnzyme

Technologies of the FUTURe for low-cost ENZYMEs for environment-friendly products

FuturEnzyme will provide benefits on several levels:

Consumers

↓
Products processed according to ecological principles and with better properties.

Planet

↓
Change mitigation, pollution prevention, protection and recovery of biodiversity and ecosystems and circular economy.

Companies

↓
New markets and gain better visibility.